

SLANG ANTHROPONYMS IN THE UZBEK LANGUAGE

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ABSTRACT

Slang may be used by members of a particular profession, such as musicians, surgeons, soldiers, or sailors, but it doesn't really have anything to do with reputation or rank. This suggests that slang is a unit that is simpler to comprehend than jargon. Jargon is a term used in a profession whose meaning can only be understood by those who work in that industry. Unlike slang and jargon, which are made up of randomly chosen mutated components of one or more natural languages of a very small and restricted professional or social group, argot is a special criminal language. Slang is often replenished with vocabulary borrowed from other professional groups. Unfortunately, there are a lot of words included in the student slang from the lexicon of drug addicts, which in turn partly indicates that this particular segment of the population is a behavioral guide for a certain part of the students. In addition, about 30% of the words in student slang are taboo vocabulary related to sex.

Uzbek anthroponymy is based on modern scientific methods studies devoted to learning began to appear in the 60s of the last century. An anthroponym is not just a word that distinguishes an individual from among similar ones. The concepts fixed in anthroponyms are a reflection of the features of objects, properties and relations of reality. The history of names is closely connected with the history, culture, ideology of the society in which they are created. Personal proper names have a national flavor to a greater extent than common nouns. That is why anthroponyms are so actively used in proverbs, sayings, literary texts (the so-called "speaking" names and surnames), in criminal jargon and in modern youth slang. The main functions of the anthroponym are traditionally considered identification, nominative and differentiating, however, in slang, its secondary functions are activated: social, emotional, address, expressive, aesthetic and stylistic.

Қотиб қолмоқ – to be drunk. The usual meaning of the word *қотиб қолмоқ* is to freeze, stiffen. This word does not need a direct addition and is used throughout Uzbekistan.

Example: – *Қотиб қолдингми?* (Are you drunk?)

Синмоқ- the original meaning - to break.

Синдираман- Break or beat - used as a threat.

Телефонингни бермасанг мен сени синдираман (If you don't give me a cell, phone, I'll break you).

Урғочи- A very rude word. I think it's something between a bitch and a hen. The original meaning is female. Example: -Урғочинг борми? (Do you have a girlfriend?)

Ўзича - generally speaking, means "in one's own way". But in slang, this word becomes a noun and is used to refer to an arrogant person who puts himself above other people. Very often used in relation to girls, they say she refused me, here it is! What does she think of herself!- *Ўзича-е, ким деб ҳисоблайди, ўзини?!*

The language of communication between merchants and the relationship of individual social groups used to hide one's identity from others among small social groups. Definitions of this nature, similar in content, are also given in the works of E.D.Suleimenova, Yu.S. Maslova, N.V. Vasilyeva, V.I. Belikov. In general, it is obvious that jargons and slang in the Uzbek language are in many cases used in Russian originally. In the encyclopedia of the Uzbek language at the moment there are 160 words associated with theft in the youth speech, 85 words and phrases associated with deceit, concealment [1, 140].

It is known that slangs by their nature are words that are used among people of a narrow circle, united by common interests, occupations or position in society, and which do not always form a low style. For example, sometimes in newspapers and magazines there is often information related to the activities of police officers, such as the operation "Burgut", "operation of the second direction". Of course, these are also not understandable phenomena, and some slang, after completing their task, obviously ceases to exist in the language. So, for example, the names of military equipment or geographical names, after they become known and understood by the whole youth, cease to exist as slang or jargon. Some words "die" very quickly and are replaced by new ones; others live for centuries and sometimes get into the literary language from slang.

The use of non-literary elements in speech - vulgarisms, swear words, jargon, slang - is typical for students of almost any era. However, the activity of non-normative word usage has never been as high as in the communication of modern schoolchildren, and the problem of speech purity has never been raised as acutely as in the last 5-10 years.

What specific invective (cf. *invectivaoratio* "rough speech") and slang lexemes are most characteristic of the speech of students in recent years? If the set of traditionally used invectives is relatively stable and mainly limited by offensive assessments of the mental abilities and external behavior of the addressee (fool, idiot, psycho, etc.), then school/university and - more broadly - youth slang is characterized by much more significant diversity and variability [2, 20]. Unfortunately, it was not possible for us to provide a large number of examples of Kazakh slang.

"Узун қулоқ" (rumors). Translating this slang literally, we get "long ear", which should mean that having "long ears" you can hear a lot of information.

"Чурвақалар" (children). It is worth noting that this slang is quite outdated for youth slang, and now it is mainly used by older people in their speech.

“Абитур” (applicant). The Russian word entrant has been transformed into a diminutive абитур.

“Мусор- ахлат- rubbish - ballyhoo, fiddle-de-dee” are rare case when all three languages describe a word according to the same principle, a set of meaningless letters and sounds that mean nonsense, nonsense.

“Тўнка” (greedy person). In many stories and works, greedy people are described as plain and fat, obviously implying that greedy people eat a lot and do not share with anyone. The Kazakh version was no exception, karyn means belly, bai means a rich person.

“Онасининг қизи” (cowardly, spineless). The literal translation of this phrase can be confusing. It in this case is translated as inert, weak character, and sheshe - mother.

“Шайтон сув” (alcohol, vodka). The word “шайтон” is an adjective meaning naughty, mischievous. “Сув” is translated as water, liquid. Vodka, like all alcohol, has a detrimental effect on a person, changes his character, and makes him intractable or aggressive.

Slangisms of the Uzbek language are formed mainly on the basis of a noun; other parts of speech (adjectives, verbs, etc.) are not activated in the associative base of the carrier of Uzbek youth slang due to a rather limited vocabulary of the literary norm of the language for most slang users [3, 17].

During the survey, we found that the vast majority of slang lexemes belong to the semantic field "Education" (concepts and ideas of school life, the realities of the school environment). The core of education slang, used for many decades, consists of such words as: Камчатка, Чукотка (back desks), шпора (cheat sheet), доза (задание на дом, homework), etc.

Our survey showed that the following slang lexemes are most regularly repeated in the speech of students in recent years: tin, cool, cool, cool, hangout, count up, nishtyak, chip, dude, dumb, sucks, fly away, stir up.

To the question "Why do you use slang in your speech?" the following responses were given (responses are in descending order).

1. It's fashionable.
2. Not to be different from others.
3. With the help of such words, you can emotionally convey what you feel.
4. One word says it all.
5. With the help of slang, you can transfer information to each other so that others (more often adults) do not understand what is being said.
6. In our circle, this is customary.

Many students in Uzbekistan use English words as slang. More often there are such words as: тичэ (teacher), фэйс (face), супер (super), гирл (girl), etc. Uzbek words are not used as often as English ones: хуш келганский (welcome), бўғирсоқ (fat person), чёткий from Russian word (cool).

Comparing the slang and idiomatic expressions of the English and Russian languages, we came to the conclusion that in both languages slang is very common and in each of them it makes up about 15-20% of the total vocabulary of an ordinary person. Having drawn analogies with the Uzbek language, we came to the conclusion that Uzbek slang is much different from both Russian and English. If Russian, like English, is full of slang expressions,

then, in turn, there is little slang in the Uzbek language, and most of them are borrowed from neighboring languages.

According to experts, this situation can be explained by two reasons. One of the explanations is that the Uzbek language itself is more colloquial, that is, it does not abound in complex phrases and scientific terms of Uzbek origin, as, indeed, in all languages, since scientific terms are almost always international. Another reason for the small volume of slang is the very blurred boundaries in the Uzbek language between slang and ordinary or literary language. In part, this is quite understandable, because the Uzbek language, although it is old, most of the time existed in oral form, due to historical circumstances. From a linguistic point of view, relatively recently formed, with a mass of borrowed words, Uzbek writing is undergoing constant changes, acquiring a mass of new words.

Due to all of the above reasons, it is very difficult to trace and identify slang and jargon. After analyzing the above circumstances, we came to the conclusion that slang, professional jargon and slang are present mainly in the "old" languages with a relatively long-established written language.

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